

Comparison of the History of Psychology of Türkiye with the History of World Psychology

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Abstract

The origins of the Istanbul University Experimental Psychology Chair may be traced back to the year 1937. The inception of the Istanbul University Experimental Psychology Chair has also taken place this year. In the aforementioned year, Dr. Wilhelm Peters, a renowned psychology professor at the University of Jena, was extended an invitation to join Istanbul University. This invitation came subsequent to his relocation to England, where he sought safety from the oppressive regime of Nazi Germany. He was appointed as the Director of the recently founded

Pedagogical Institute and also assumed the position of Head of the Chair of Experimental Psychology. Additionally, Peters held the position of Head of the Department of Experimental Psychology at Istanbul University. The individual in question undertook the necessary basic research for the construction of an independent Experimental Psychology Institute, separate from the Pedagogical Institute, for a period of 15 years. This work was carried out until the year 1957, at which point the individual departed from Turkey. Additionally, he successfully finalized the development of both the Psychology Laboratory and the Psychology Library that are associated with this Institute. Under his direction, the basis of the tradition of scientific inquiry in psychology has consistently been established. This included the completion of undergraduate theses using the experiential approach, engagement in the application of psychology, and undertaking collaborative research endeavors in the field of psychology alongside other students. In the first edition of the Journal of Psychological and Pedagogical Studies, which was published in 1940, Professor Peters freely recognizes the diligent efforts and unexpectedly noteworthy immediate accomplishments during this nascent period. Professor Peters and Professor Mümtaz Turhan, both esteemed academics, played a pivotal role in advancing the field of psychology as an empirical discipline at Istanbul University. Following Professor Peters' visit to Germany in 1952, Professor Mumtaz Turhan was appointed as the Chair of Experimental Psychology. Furthermore, in the year 1960, with the finalization of the institute's organizational structure, Professor Mumtaz Turhan assumed the position of Director at the Institute of Experimental Psychology. Professor Dr. M. Turhan, who has two doctorates from Frankfurt and Cambridge Universities, is credited with a substantial body of intellectual property including over a dozen copyrighted and translated publications. Additionally, Professor Dr. Turhan has played a significant role in the academic development of around five faculty members.

Keywords: *History of Psychology in Turkey, History of World Psychology, Science of Psychology, History of Psychology in Turkey and the World, History of Psychology*

Introduction

He shown a lack of hesitation in making various sacrifices in order to further their education. Historically, the positions of General Psychology Chair and Experiential Psychology Chair within our academic community have been historically occupied by individuals from the field of Psychology. Following the retirement of Professor Tunç, the position of committee chairperson was taken by Sabri Esat Siyavuşgil. It is vital to get knowledge about the visiting

lecturers who sometimes provide significant contributions to the psychological education imparted in Istanbul.

One of the individuals in question is Professor Walter R. Miles, who served as a faculty member at Yale University from 1954 until 1957. The list also includes prominent individuals such as Professor NH Pronko, Professor Haines, Professor Hollander, Professor Reed, and Professor Goldberg, the latter of whom had a tenure of just one year. All individuals who have gained prominence in their respective areas of competence merit recognition as scientists due to their significant contributions to the psychology education system in Turkey throughout their tenure in the country. The magazine titled "Psychology Studies" has maintained a consistent publishing record from the inception of the Institute and Chair, therefore providing a convenient means to stay updated on the most recent advancements and research in the field of psychology in Istanbul. The production of "Psychology Studies" has been ongoing since the inception of the Institute and Chair. The publication in question was first released in two separate volumes under the title "Pedagogical Institute, Psychology and Pedagogical Studies," and its original editor was Professor Petersen. The aforementioned books were first published in the years 1940 and 1962, correspondingly. In 1956, Dr. Walter RT Miles, an esteemed professor, assumed the role of editor for the magazine, resulting in a change of its title to "Istanbul University Experimental Psychology Studies." A cumulative sum of 15 volumes were produced up through the year 1985.

This 19-volume collection, inclusive of two previously published volumes, may be regarded as an extensive compilation of psychological research undertaken in Istanbul. With a total of 17 volumes and three extra publications, it encompasses a significant portion of the study conducted in this field. Based on the information provided in the "Bibliography" appendix and the "Completed Studies" sections of volumes 11, 12, and 13 of the magazines published in 1972, it can be inferred that there were an estimated 733 undergraduate theses, 21 doctorate theses, 81 books related to copyright and translation, and 120 scientific papers. The text was published in a language other than Turkish. One notable inquiry started in 1962 under the guidance of Professor Osgood, who had a faculty position at the University of Illinois. The study was concluded in the year 1972, and the results were then integrated into the publication titled "Intercultural Universals of Emotional Meaning" (1975), authored by Professors Osgood, May, and Miron.

[Researches on "Psychological Characteristics of Endocrine Diseases" Beginning in 1963](#)

The investigation of the psychological attributes associated with endocrine disorders, which started in 1963 at the Department of Endocrinology within the Cerrahpaşa Faculty of

Medicine, has continued until the present day. The dissemination of research findings in the field of medicine often involves their presentation at medical conferences and subsequent publication in journals written in languages other than Turkish, alongside publications published in the Turkish language. The research, which started in 1975 at the Ministry of Health and Social Welfare 6 Point Rehabilitation Center for the Visually Impaired, was delivered by four academic staff members during a seminar conducted during the White Stick Week for the Blind.

The contributions made by Beglan Torol to the field of psychology education after 1937 are discussed in the works of W. Authors, Engin, M. Turhan, and B. Torol. These works include "Experimental Psychology" by W. Authors, Engin, M. Turhan, and B. Torol, as well as "General Psychology" by M. Torol. Tunç, ES Siyavuşgil, and N. Arkun served as chairpersons. Subsequently, in 1981, the department transitioned into a unified entity including four primary divisions within the field of psychology. The sequence of department heads proceeded with B. Torol, A. Ark, Elizabeth Cantez, and Nathan Telman. The decade of the 1930s saw the emergence of multiple sclerosis (MS). In 1938, the literary works of Tunç, W. James, and S. Freud were translated into the language of Siyavuşgil by an unknown translator. The individual responsible for these contributions was Piaget. The laboratory associated with Peter's Experimental Psychology Laboratory was responsible for doing research that was subsequently published in the "Journal of Psychology and Pedagogical Studies" in 1940. Additionally, W. Peters established the "Journal of Experimental Psychology Studies". The year 1956 saw the first release of Miles in printed format. The aforementioned scholarly publication, now recognized as Psychology Studies, retains its original nomenclature and remains an active outlet for academic dissemination.

Methodology

During the 1960s and 1970s, scholars in the area of psychology in Istanbul, Ankara, and the Aegean Region directed their efforts on the education of students and the localization of different examinations in Turkey, mostly via PhD programs. The user's text is too short to be rewritten in an academic manner. After departing from Istanbul, the individual in question relocated to Germany, where they experienced the pinnacle of their professional achievements while collaborating with Gustav Deuchler within the period of Nazi governance. Hence, although Anschutz's endeavors in Istanbul are often regarded as the first introduction of experimental psychology and the establishment of an experimental psychology laboratory in Turkey, it would be inaccurate to deem it as the definitive inception of psychology in the country. Anschutz's

engagement in Istanbul occurred throughout the 19th century. Prior to the founding of Darülfünun-i Osmani in 1869, Aziz Efendi delivered a lecture titled "Emcazi Ekalim" at the aforementioned institution. The seminar was held in the evening and was accessible to the general public, with the purpose of examining the month of Ramadan (Yıldırım, 1998, p. 94). This course is widely acknowledged as the first instance of a psychology course being offered inside a university setting. According to Özbaydar (1973, p. 219), it has been documented that Babanzade Naim Bey delivered a series of psychology courses with a focus on theology, which were referred to as "Im-ün Nefs," after the 1908 Revolution. The precise origins of the first book or journal article on psychology remain unknown. It is not unexpected that the first publication of this literary piece predates the year 1915 by a considerable number of years. Sami Kayral (1953) has authored a total of 29 works, out of which 11 are translations. In contrast, Nuri Bilgin (1988) has a body of work consisting of 27 publications, with 9 of them being translations. Both writers agree that the aggregate quantity of translated literary works amounts to 11. The earliest of these works is Yusuf Kemal's book titled "Gayet-ül Beyan Fi Perakende-ül- İnsan Yahut Im-i Ahval-i Ruh." The first publication of the work occurred in 1876. The first instance of translation from a language other than Arabic occurred with the publication of "Ruh-ül Akvam" by Abdullah Cevdet in Egypt in 1907. The text in question constituted a translation of LeBon's renowned publication, *Psychologie des Foules*. Nevertheless, the limited availability of comprehensive scholarly research in the field of traditional psychology precludes a definitive understanding of the existence of earlier studies in this domain. As there was no record of doing such a search. The responsibility of teaching the psychology courses was assigned to Mustafakip Tunç and Ali Haydar Taner. Ali Haydar Taner, a professional pedagogue, was affiliated with Darülfünun until 1924, during which time he imparted knowledge in the field of "experimental psychology".

Mustafa Tunç furthered his studies in psychology inside the philosophy department, with the aim of establishing a conventional framework for the subject influenced by the philosophical perspectives of Henri Bergson. The year 1933 has significant intellectual importance for both Germany and Turkey, serving as a pivotal period for both nations. Following the ascension of the Nazi Party to power in Germany, a considerable number of university professors were compelled to relinquish their positions due to the discriminatory policies implemented by the party. These policies specifically targeted public officials of Jewish heritage or those who were married to individuals of Jewish blood. As a result of the University Reform implemented in Turkey during the same year, Istanbul Darülfünun was effectively shut down and afterwards replaced by Istanbul University. The university's teaching faculty was categorized into three distinct groups: those who had previously worked at Darülfünun without experiencing termination, young individuals who

had been sent elsewhere to further their studies, and academics hailing from other nations. The individual entrusted with the examination of Darülfünun and the subsequent presentation of reform requirements in a comprehensive report was Albert Malche, a Swiss citizen. He assumed the role of overseeing the recruitment process for individuals within the global education community. Malche reached out to the "Solidarity Association of German Professors Abroad" (Notgemeinschaft deutscher Wissenschaftler im Ausland) in Zurich under the guidance of Doctor Philipp Schwartz.

A decision was then made to extend an invitation to Adhémar Gelb. As stated by Arkonac (1995), Gelb, who was escaping from Germany, agreed to the proposition. The work of Buiddia Arkonac is original and does not draw on any other sources. It is indeterminable if Mr. Gelb has accepted the offer. Gelb is well recognized for being among the minority of faculty members who chose not to emigrate from Germany after their expulsion. On January 15, 1937, Wilhelm Peters was extended an offer, which he duly accepted, to become the leadership of the recently created "Pedagogical Institute" in Istanbul. Consequently, Peters arrived in Istanbul to commence his duties.

The use of primary sources within the discipline of history should not be restricted only to the objective of debunking misconceptions propagated by concise explanatory writings. Additionally, he will possess the ability to elucidate the sources that had influence in the genesis of these "legends". The political stance of Mümtaz Turhan was influenced by the philosophical perspective that reduced psychology to "experimental psychology" and the "exaggerated" statements about his education, while Anschutz was credited as the "founder" of psychology in Turkey. The development of an individual's identity might be argued to be shaped by certain ideological concepts, such as Gelb's or Peters' perspectives on "refugees" or the concealment of Peters' return. The use of original sources is regarded as the paramount and dependable foundation for comprehending such stuff. The study of the history of science necessitates a comprehensive reevaluation of historical events. However, without access to suitable resources, these reevaluations run the risk of deviating significantly from the accurate depiction of historical fact, perhaps leading to erroneous interpretations.

Literature Review

The process of reconstructing historical events is crucial in the pursuit of studying the history of science. During the 19th century, the discipline of psychology emerged as an

independent and separate scientific domain. Theories on human nature were present in both Eastern and Western scientific traditions until the second quarter of the 20th century, although coincidentally. The process of modernisation has led to its adoption in countries outside the Western world as well. The emergence of this recently established scientific discipline has been seen over the course of the last decade, mostly influenced by the structured framework prevalent in the United States. For a considerable duration, this subject matter has garnered significant attention and scrutiny. As a result of advancements in this particular field of study, it has become feasible to bypass the knowledge included within conventional sources and access historical periods predating the contemporary era. Consequently, there occurred a progressive shift in the comprehension and subsequent interpretation of a discipline within the realm of psychology that had hitherto been entirely unfamiliar to society. It may be argued that this phenomenon has occurred to some extent. It might be argued that a state of "disenchantment" has occurred.

Furthermore, the emphasis is placed on the theses pertaining to the field of psychology, rather than being limited to certain nations. Brock posits a thesis asserting the compatibility between his paper on the intersection of psychology and liberal democracy in Cuba. Another notable characteristic of the articles is their worldwide scope, as they not only focus on the national context of the examined country but also explore the interrelations between other nations. In the "Introduction" section of the book, Adrian Brock, the editor, delves into the field of psychology and its connection to the dominant influence of the United States in the historical development of psychology (Brock, pp. 1-13). The book's notable features include a Comprehensive Index and an extensive Bibliography appended to each piece. The primary contention underscored in the papers is to the existence of a distinct "psychology industry" in North America, which has gained recognition outside its borders, including other nations.

This particular field of research, which has been imported from Western countries, is assessed in the context of political advancements and reconciliation endeavors. throughout this particular context, it is possible to enumerate the notable and interconnected subjects discussed throughout the articles in the following manner: It is feasible to categorize them into several headings.

Psychology and Cultural Imperialism

There is a prevailing argument that cultural imperialism and the importation of psychology exhibit comparable characteristics. Numerous scientific investigations pertaining to this particular

field of study, which has been adopted from nations such as Europe and North America, are being conducted inside countries such as India and England. Within this particular context, it is essential to assess the assertion that it lacks pertinence to the topic at hand. Furthermore, Kurt Danzinger provides an elucidation of the conflation of subjects and ideas in a collaborative research endeavor conducted with psychology experts from Indonesia (Danzinger, p. 22). Additionally, Cecilia Taiana offers an account of the inability to establish French supremacy in the theories proposed by Wundt and Freud (Taiana, p. 49).

Results

In her scholarly work discussing the historical advancements within the realm of psychology in Turkey, Aydan Güler characterizes Turkish psychology as lacking a sense of historical context, cultural depth, and social integration. He provided a description of the influence exerted by American psychology on Turkey in the following manner: The text refers to the book with the identifier "241". The pervasive influence and widespread acceptance of American psychology is of such magnitude that Turkish psychologists have established a dedicated position in Western experimental psychology at a Turkish academic institution.

This paper presents a comprehensive analysis of the extensive historical progression leading up to the establishment of a certain entity. According to the author (p. 76), there is no need for individuals to engage in any action or even contemplate it. The field of psychology in the United States is not only influential in terms of cultural imperialism, but it also has significant military power. Furthermore, its existence is likewise connected to the aforementioned fact (p. 163).

Localization and Universalization

Localization has been consistently highlighted as a significant concern within the realm of international psychology throughout several research. The prevailing perspective within American psychology claims that psychology exhibits universality, implying that its principles and theories are applicable across different cultural contexts worldwide. This pertains to the field of American psychology. Nevertheless, there is a prevalent argument in several nations suggesting that the inherent incongruity between psychology and society necessitates the localization of psychology. According to the collaborative work of John Hogan and Thomas P. Vaccaro, as documented in

their scholarly studies conducted outside the borders of the United States, there exists a notable disregard for non-English written works inside the American rhetoric of universality (Hogan & Vaccaro, p. 133). Currently, several nations, particularly those in the Arab world, have established connections with the field of psychology, including the subfield of developmental psychology. There is a prevailing assumption that the United States is experiencing a progressive decline in its prominence within the realm of psychology. In contrast, Steauble examines the positioning of psychology in the context of cultural imperialism. The author classified "local psychologies" as a kind of "anti-colonial discourse" (p. 200). In the context of localization, it is worth noting that Brock has raised significant objections about Paranjpe's written work. Paranjpe stated that some appellations originating from the Indian intellectual heritage and old Sanskrit manuscripts constitute an integral component of the historical trajectory of psychology. Brock is among the philosophers and scientists who made significant contributions to the development of the field of psychology. According to the Buddha, those who cannot be classified as members of an unregulated religious group would include figures like Confucius (p. 238).

In addition to the inherent restlessness and perceived flaws within human nature, there exists a corresponding virtuous aspect. During the first phase, there is a limited understanding on the specific element of the individual to associate with. However, as the process of release progresses into the second stage, there is a notable development akin to a budding phenomenon. In what manner did James articulate the description of this process? Can it identify with the direction that is prepared to undergo evolutionary changes, such as? The direction denoting values is situated in close proximity to the neighboring direction and serves as a seamless extension of it. A notable distinction lies in the fact that values that are already existent in the realm of the "earthly" orientation are indicative of higher values. According to Ellenberger (1994: 298), The word used by James in this context denotes "an increase in quantity while maintaining the same level of quality." The phenomenon characterized by a rapid growth of emotional and sensory attributes is referred to as "subtle senses and emotions" within the field of psychology. According to Frager and Fadiman (2002: 470), Ibrahim is a psychologist who has placed significant emphasis on the significance of individuals' spiritual well-being. Maslow discussed several levels of consciousness, including what he referred to as "peak experiences," which had been recognized for a considerable period of time. The phenomenon of experiences that reach their pinnacle with sudden intensity, like to lightning illuminating a gloomy night, and the remarkable lives that make a lasting impression on our collective awareness. According to Maslow (1996: 111), throughout his early years, he developed a romantic affection for his cousin, who eventually became his spouse. Transpersonal psychology, as a branch of psychology, encompasses the contributions of notable

figures like as William James, Charles Tart, Abraham Maslow, and Stanislav Grof. These individuals have furthered our knowledge of the human experience by drawing upon the insights and experiences of contemporary psychology as a whole. According to Atak (2019, p. 135), Hence, the examination of the spiritual dimension from a psychological standpoint in Western societies has been constrained. In order to unravel the enigma of humanity The issue has been extensively examined by Islamic academics and mystics in studies conducted many centuries ago.

Argument

The historical development of psychology within the Islamic tradition dates back to the 8th century CE. Islamic scholars and philosophers made significant contributions to the field, exploring many aspects of the human mind and behavior. These early pioneers laid the foundation for the subsequent growth and advancement of psychology in Islamic societies. The Evolution of Psychology in the Islamic World 2.1. The Seljuks and Ottomans endeavored to provide treatment for those suffering from mental illness inside hospital settings, known as bimarhanes. They used many therapeutic approaches, including sound therapy using water, music therapy, and occupational therapy. The societal need for psychology was minimal. The practitioners of Sufism possess an inherent inclination towards providing guidance, healing, and psychological support, sometimes referred to as advice, treatment, or psychotherapy. Dervish lodges, often known as spiritual development institutions, serve significant roles within the spiritual domain, primarily of a psychological nature. According to Merter (2020), leaders within society are responsible for generating resolutions to the mental and emotional challenges encountered by people. Kindi is recognized as the pioneering scientist who conducted research in the field of psychology within the Islamic world. Al-Kindi, a prominent scholar who lived during the 9th century (d. 866), dedicated his efforts to the study of sleep, dreams, and the alleviation of melancholy. The presence of unregulated rage and sensual feelings is evident in the literary piece titled "Ways to Get Rid of Sorrow". The individual discussed the neurotic issues they had instigated and explored potential strategies for their resolution. According to McCarthy (2017: 28-41), Kindi has authored seventeen books that focus on the concept of the *ilmun* soul. According to McCarthy's study in psychology (1962, pp. 81-91), Kindi's birth took place in the year 801 in the city of Kufa. The scholars who received their education in the towns of Basra and Kufa were admitted to *Beytu'l Hikme*, also referred to as *Jamaat*. The translator Kindi has rendered several Greek and Indian literary masterpieces into the Arabic language. The provided statement pertains to the act of interpretation.

Kindi, in the course of fulfilling his responsibilities, incorporated his own reflections into the texts that he translated.

He significantly contributed to the advancement of notable scholars, like Ebu Ma'sher Ja'far bin Muhammed Belhi, Hasnaveyh, and Naftuye, in their respective fields. The individual in question received backing from adherents of the Mutezile sect. Subsequently, during the reign of Caliph Mutawakkil, he departed from the palace and faced expulsion from Beyt-ul-Hikme, with his literary works being seized. The individual's death occurred in the city of Baghdad in the year 866 as a result of a persistent rheumatic ailment. Belhi, whose life spanned till 934, is widely recognized as the pioneering figure in the classification of psychiatric diseases into the categories of neurotic and psychotic. The individual in question has the professional designation of a psychiatrist. The impression of body-mental health is prominently underscored due to the variations and distinctiveness of nature and temperament. The book titled "Mesâlih-ül-Ebdan wal-Enfûs" was released in 1982 by Fuat Sezgin, a renowned Islamic scholar and researcher in the field of civilisation history. This work is divided into two sections, namely Medicine and Mental Health. (Belhi, 2012: 28) In 1998, Sezgin (Belhî, 2012: 31) released an additional edition of the aforementioned book. Belhi's birth occurred in the year 849 according to the Hijri calendar (H.235), in the city of Belh. The individual embarked on extensive travels to several urban centers in pursuit of knowledge acquisition. Notably, he acquired expertise in a diverse range of academic disciplines, including physics, astronomy, mathematics, history, geography, medicine, literature, fiqh, and kalam. Upon the completion of his scientific studies, he subsequently returned to Belh. Simultaneously, his appellation started to resonate ubiquitously. The individual's demise occurred in Belh in the year 934 (H.322). The author produced a substantial body of scholarly work including several disciplines such as psychology, physics, astronomy, mathematics, history, geography, medicine, literature, law, and religion. Regrettably, just a solitary piece from his extensive repertoire has survived the test of time and remains accessible in contemporary times. The Istanbul Süleymaniye Library has two copies of Mesâlih-ül-Ebdân wal-Enfûs, a work pertaining to the field of medical science. These copies are catalogued under the reference number 3741 in the Hagia Sophia department of the library.

According to Haris al Muhasibi, the author of *The Psychological Foundations of Religious Behavior* (d.857), the act of bragging has the potential to obstruct one's emotional and spiritual perception. This individual engages in malevolent actions. Despite seeing his actions as beneficial, he associates his errors with causing harm. The individual in question has a tendency to minimize their own errors and transgressions, while relying on personal intuition for guidance. Muhasibi, in

his seminal work published in 2009, has been recognized as a prominent figure in the realm of spirituality within the Islamic domain. His contributions encompass a comprehensive examination of various aspects of human existence, including states of consciousness, rationality, cognition, desires, and the impact of impulses, all of which are analyzed within the framework of Qur'anic principles. According to Hökelekli (2006: 410), Muhasibi's birthplace was Basra in the year 781. The individual established residence in Baghdad and allocated a portion of their lifespan inside that location. The time in which he resided included the Abbasid era, which is often regarded as the finest age of intellectual enlightenment. He is among the first mystics whose literary works have endured to the contemporary day.

Ahl as-Sunnat Ghazali, the prominent figure in the realm of Sufism, derived significant advantages from his literary contributions. Hadith, Kalam, and Muhasibi, esteemed figures in the field of methodology and revered as imams in the realm of Sufism, first affiliated themselves with the Mu'tazila sect. Despite first adopting these views, he eventually renounced them. During this particular era, notable individuals such as Ma'ruf Karhi, Seriyy es-Sakati, Junayd al-Baghdadi, and Imam Ahmed bin Hanbal were prominent figures. Muhasibi's demise occurred in Baghdad in the year 243 AH (857 CE).

In the literary piece titled *Tıbbu'r Rûhânî*, the author identifies three distinct categories of individuals who were found to possess an appealing taste. The concept of the mind encompasses several forms of spirit, including animal spirit and plant spirit. The existence of animal and plant spirits is believed to be in service of the rational spirit. The responsibility of the vegetative spirit pertains to the physical organism. The responsibility is in nourishing the animalistic essence, which serves as the origin of fury, and assuring its growth and procreation. Conversely, its purpose is in aiding the logical mind in conquering carnal inclinations. The vegetative and animal souls experience mortality alongside their respective capacities, however the intellectual soul is characterized by its immortality. Consequently, it may be argued that all religions and philosophical perspectives universally denounce base wants and see them as morally reprehensible. Different strategies are used to address these demands and needs, but it is essential to refrain from beyond the limits set by rationality and to uphold the principles of human dignity (Razi, 2019:17-20). Razi's birth took place in the year 864 in Rey, Iran. The individual had a keen interest in a diverse range of academic disciplines, including music, mathematics, astronomy,

chemistry, philosophy, and medicine. Due to his inclination towards the field of medicine, he pursued a course of study in medical education. Razi, who gained prominence by diligent efforts throughout his tenure working among the populace, undertook the role of head physician at the hospital in the city of Rey. During this particular era, because to his extensive research in the fields of medicine and medical education, he ascended to the esteemed position of head physician at Baghdad Hospital, which was well renowned during that time. The individual in question was granted a commission and dedicated a significant portion of his lifespan at this location. The encyclopedia known as *Hâvî*, which was authored in the domain of medicine, had the status of being the foremost authoritative source of reference within its discipline until the 17th century. Razi had a significant impact on the field of medical research by pioneering the integration of chemistry into the realm of medicine. Razi, in the last stages of his life, returned to the city of Rey where he ultimately died away in the year 925.

According to the works of Farabi, a prominent philosopher who lived during the 10th century, the process of cultivating the intellect is referred to as teaching, while the development of the soul is denoted as education. He developed a framework for organizing educational and training programs focused on the essence and characteristics of human beings. The topic of individual variations, which has significance in contemporary psychology, pertains to Fârâbî's educational background. The existence of this concept is already acknowledged within the field of philosophy. According to Yavuzer (1997: 20), Farabi's birth took place in 873 in the city of Farab, located in Turkestan. Firstly, he is a philosopher of Turkish origin who adheres to the Islamic faith. The individual successfully concluded his elementary education in Farab, followed by his madrasah education in Baghdad. He conducted philosophical inquiry at Harran. During this period, he engaged in the study of Aristotle's writings in conjunction with Yuhanna bin Haylan. The individual in question was hosted by the king of Hamadani in the city of Aleppo. The individual in question embraced Aristotle's conceptualization of substance and form. As a result of his academic pursuits in the discipline of medicine, he has authored scholarly works pertaining to several pharmaceutical substances. The individual engaged in the translation and study of the literary and philosophical works of ancient Greek scholars, effectively rendering them into the Arabic language. European scientists engage in the study of Fârâbî's works as a means to acquire knowledge in this domain. Fârâbî's works have been present in Europe for an extended period of time due to this particular rationale. He was employed as an instructor at many academic

institutions. Numerous scholarly investigations have been conducted on the medieval Western region, wherein it is noted that Farabi's death occurred in Damascus in the year 950.

Ibn Miskeveyh, a scholar who lived until 1030, examines the field of psychology through the lens of metaphysics and the faculties of the human soul. The foundation of his psychological framework is upon the notion that the soul has a spiritual nature grounded on metaphysical principles. The primary subject of this study centers on the concept of achieving immortality. According to Miskeveyh (year), the human soul, also known as the soul, is neither a biological entity nor a fortuitous attachment to the body. When an object or entity assumes a certain form, another object or entity assumes its position. In contrast, the soul has the capacity to assimilate many types of knowledge, while without the ability to manifest in any tangible or corporeal form. Moreover, the soul has the capacity to see and comprehend intelligible forms. In this particular scenario, the acquisition of information that surpasses sensory perception and relies on an individual's intangible, non-material understanding suggests its acquisition via spiritual faculties. The issue at hand also pertains to tangible entities. This does not imply that an equivalent degree of physical capability is seen as self-referential. The corporeal form comprehends the metaphysical nature of the soul. In the absence of this condition, the cognitive representation of the individual in question would be irretrievably compromised, since he would lack the capacity to rectify his errors. According to Miskeveyh (2017: 13-14), Mustafa Atak Miskeveyh's birthplace was Rey, Iran, in the year 936. Miskeveyh, who refrained from engaging in discourse pertaining to literature, history, morals, and philosophy, adhered to the aforementioned method. He gained first recognition via his written works on the subject of moral philosophy. In contrast to Farabi, he places more emphasis on practical application rather than theoretical deliberations. He used a pragmatic approach. In order to reconcile the tenets of Islam with the philosophical doctrines of Plato and Aristotle. Miskeveyh's demise occurred in the year 1030 while his occupation in the urban center of Isfahan.

According to the renowned scholar Ibn-i Sina, who passed away in 1037, he posited that a kid who exhibits harmonious biological functioning is likely to manifest exceptional physical attractiveness, with the development of a well-balanced personality and sound mental well-being. Initially, it is important for the infant to engage in gradual movements in order to enhance his physical strength. According to Yavuzer (1997: 18), it is advisable to facilitate the child's transition

into sleep by engaging in the practice of singing a lullaby while the adult is also resting. Through the formulation of these concepts, he established the fundamental principles of child and adolescent psychology. He is credited with being the first to address the conditions of hysteria, Avicenna, and depressive disorders. Abduladil asserts that Ibn Sina's birthplace was the city of Bukhara in the year 980 (Abduladil, 2007: 37). Avicenna, the progeny of Sina, is recognized throughout Western academia under the appellation of Avicenna. Abdullah Bin, a clerk employed in the Samanullar Palace. Ibn Sina, well known as Avicenna, was the son of a man named Sinai. Natili and O were provided with guidance by İsmail Zahit, who happens to be Natili's father. Contributions have been made across several academic disciplines, including geometry, logic, canon law, consumables, syntax, medical, and natural sciences. The palace, which served as a conduit for the dissemination of Aristotle's philosophy through Al-Farabi's al-Ibane, acquired knowledge of his metaphysics and provided medical care to the ailing prince of Bukhara, so gaining access to the library. The philosophical ideas of Aristotle were transmitted via the work of Farabi in his book al-Ibane. He developed expertise in the whole of the Greek language by an extensive study of the works of philosophers and naturalists from Anatolia. The author produced in excess of 450 scholarly publications including a diverse range of subjects, with 240 of these works having remained extant to the present day. Out of the total number of recorded papers, 150 are to the field of philosophy, while 40 are specifically related to medicine.

His published works in the domains of philosophy and science are widely recognized as his most notable contributions. The work known as Kitabu's-ifa, also referred to as the Book of Healing, together with ElKanun fi't-Tb, generally recognized as the Law of Medicine, provides a thorough examination including several facets of the field of medicine. During the Middle Ages, these two writings were mandated readings at academic institutions.

The book titled "El-Kanun fi't-Tb" authored by Ibn Sina, a prominent scholar who passed away in Hamadan in 1037, gained significant recognition as a textbook and was reprinted in Montpellier and Louvain until the year 1650. Ibn Hazm (d. 1064) expounded fundamental concepts pertaining to the safeguarding of mental well-being, elucidating various behavioral patterns and modes of communication used by individuals in their efforts to alleviate uneasiness and apprehension.

Ibn Hazm (d.1064) provided significant guidance on the preservation of mental well-being and exemplified many behaviors and dialogues used by those seeking to alleviate such concerns. The individual used the following visual aid to substantiate their perspective. For instance, individuals who aspire to acquire property aim to alleviate the distress associated with poverty. Similarly, those who pursue fame aim to alleviate the distress of others exerting dominance over them, and instead seek enjoyment and recognition. Their objective is to alleviate the distress of feeling deprived. Another objective is to alleviate the distress of ignorance, which can be achieved through engaging in conversation, solitude, and remaining uninformed about worldly matters. These actions serve to alleviate various anxieties. Ibn Hazm (2012: 33-34) notes that throughout history, there has been only one individual who perceives anxiety positively and does not seek to eliminate it.

Following the decree of the Abbasid monarch to incinerate his literary contributions, Ibn Hazm was compelled to depart from Seville and subsequently established his residence in Leble, where he resided until his death in 1064. The individual authored the literary work known as *Naktu'l Arus* during the duration of their residency at this location.

The study and categorization of the subject matter are quite extensive. In the first sections of the third volume of the book, the chapter titled "Acaibu'l Heart" begins by providing an overview of fundamental human instincts, emotions, desires, and inclinations. This term is used to denote theological and moral deductions derived from meticulous behavioral study. The rationality of religious beliefs and behaviors is in opposition to the capriciousness of natural phenomena. Ghazali says that the ability to exercise control over one's ideas is a fundamental need for adopting a firm stance. The book "*Meancu'l-Kuds*" explores several aspects related to the soul, including its nature, the role of the heart, intellect, and soul, as well as the concepts of movement and comprehension. The comprehensive understanding of individuals' capabilities encompasses their internal and external sensory faculties, diverse emotional states, and differing levels of cognitive consciousness. Subsequently, an analysis is undertaken to examine the attributes that delineate the prophet's extraordinary cognitive capacity. The Holy Mind might be seen as the prophets' most impeccable faculty of observation or as the Holy Spirit, another appellation for this heavenly potency. According to Hokelekli (2006: 445), Ghazali's proposition on the precedence of delusion

over reaction had a pivotal role in the development of the idea of conditioned reflex, predating Pavlov's investigations by many centuries (Serbini, 2002: 296-297).

Mustafa Atak makes reference to the transcendental and spiritual component, often known as the fourth school of psychology. The phenomenon of Ghazali's enlightenment experience, along with similar experiences of enlightenment, is often known as the "holotropic state of consciousness" within the framework of interpersonal psychology. According to Grof (year), individuals in a typical state of awareness are restricted in their ability to identify with just a certain portion of their whole self. Conversely, during a holotropic condition, the physical body assumes a position of utmost constraint inside the realm of the self. The process of overcoming preconceptions enhances an individual's ability to fully use their distinctive qualities. According to Grof (2002: 22), it might be argued that Ghazali had a phase characterized by symptoms consistent with depression. According to accounts, he departed from his place of work subsequent to this event and proceeded to distance himself from his local vicinity in a manner reminiscent of evading or escaping. The individual's extensive journeys spanning over a decade have significantly contributed to the advancement of his spiritual growth. Within the realm of psychology, Ghazali astutely identified the significant challenges that would arise subsequent to undergoing the process of enlightenment. He proceeded to articulate these challenges in his subsequent written works. This essay aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of the many phases of spiritual growth that individuals may experience during their lifespan. These literary pieces have significant importance in Ghazali's body of work, and they possess inherent value that merits careful consideration and study. According to Ghazali, the heart serves as the fundamental source of all aspects of human existence. In situations characterized by pervasive corruption, the need for remedial action becomes evident. The rationale for this phenomenon is in the inherent nature of the tree, wherein its many components, such as branches, contribute to its overall structure. If the branches persist in extracting water from the tree, it will either enhance or degrade. Other organs may be seen as subordinate entities under its control. However, the heart might be seen as the only ruler. If the sultan undergoes a transformation, it is plausible that people who adhere to his ideology might also undergo a similar transition. If the Sultan exhibited corrupt behavior, it would be reasonable to infer that the general populace may have also been susceptible to corruption. Consequently, the enhancement of visual acuity, gustatory perception, and digestive function, alongside the restoration of other bodily organs, signifies a positive progression and recuperation of the heart. Therefore, the existence of a disease or disorder in any of the organs might be seen as a sign of the

existence of a more severe illness or condition. Due to this rationale, it is widely held that individuals should prioritize the allocation of their energy and effort towards the restoration of their cardiovascular system prior to addressing other bodily systems. According to Gazâlî (2011: 229), the birth of Ghazali took place in the city of Tus, located in the Khorasan province, in the year 1058. Ahmed successfully completed his formal education. Subsequently, Abu Nasr al-Adha acquired many teachings from Ismaili scholars in Jurjan and derived his theological concepts from the teachings of Abul Hasan Ash'ari. The Shafi'i school has served as a significant source of inspiration. The renowned Seljuk instructor, sometimes referred to as the Great Seljuk, had a meeting with the state's vizier, Nizamülmülk. According to a number of analysts, he demonstrated his supremacy by delivering more proficient solutions throughout this particular battle. Following the swift establishment of a commendable reputation within the area, Ghazali underwent a transition towards Sufism, subsequently directing his scholarly pursuits towards the exploration and analysis of this particular field of study. Upon embarking on his trip, he relinquished his responsibilities at the madrasa, a decision motivated by his inquisitiveness towards Sufism. Following his departure from Baghdad, he relocated his central operations to Damascus. In 1097, he embarked on a pilgrimage. In the year 1106, at the request of Nizamülmülk's offspring, permission was granted for his reinstatement at the Nizamiye Madrasa. He began his career as an educator. Subsequently, the individual in question, together with his adherents, embarked in the Tekke vessel that he had constructed, subsequently undertaking a journey back to the city of Tus. The individuals in question had a lifestyle like to that of dervishes, as documented on page 81 of the History of Psychology in Islam. The individual's death occurred in Tus, Iran during the year 1111.

Nevertheless, the proliferation of Islamic Psychology research done throughout the 1970s gained significant traction. Research on the process of Islamization within the field of psychology has been limited to the aforementioned time periods. Numerous scholarly investigations have been disseminated within the purview of this field, and several scientific conferences have been convened. During a gathering convened in the mid-1970s, Muslim social scientists congregated to discuss various topics. Among the presentations delivered during this conference, Cafer Idris delivered a lecture centered on the concept of Islamization of sciences. The present condition of the International School of Islamic Philosophy is characterized by its role as a prominent institution dedicated to the Islamization of sciences and knowledge. The Institute has successfully organized several symposiums and conferences within this domain. The current discourse involves the

assessment of Islamic psychology studies within the framework of the Islamization of knowledge. Numerous regions had analogous advancements inside this particular framework. The notion of mind and soul was proposed in 1982 by a team comprising of psychiatrists, psychologists, and theologians. The Islamic Psychiatry approach emerged within the discipline of psychiatry. The establishment of an Islamic Psychiatric Society in Kuwait was undertaken with the objective of seeking an Islamic-oriented approach to address the diseases experienced by individuals. According to Ayten (2010: 56),

According to Malik Bedri's publication titled "The Dead End of Muslim Psychologists" in 1979, the author made the following statement. The incorporation of Western psychological theories and practices is seen crucial in the adherence to the teachings of the hadiths. In contrast, he described this situation as akin to entering a reptile's den. The use of behavioral psychology approaches by al-Ghazali necessitates the modification of one's conduct. The individual asserts that his comprehension and application extend much beyond the principles he advocates for. Badri (1984) posited an approach in Islamic Psychology that received approval from Rajhid Skinner (p. 12). The examination of the ways of Islamic mystics, such as Ghazali, towards self-reflection and self-examination, is a subject of interest in modern psychology. This suggests that it would be suitable to engage in such behavior. According to Badri (year), the principal duty of a Muslim psychologist is engaging in scientific study, including the collection of objective data while disregarding value-laden myths and theories, such as psychoanalysis, that may include elements conflicting with Islamic principles.

Conclusion

Muslim psychologists have a second role, which is doing research in alignment with Islamic principles. The issue at hand pertains to the field of psychology. This paper provides an overview of the developmental trajectory of Islamic psychology. It is important to ensure that the nass filter remains unactivated throughout the implementation of various ways. One example of a therapeutic approach is behavioral therapy. The efficacy of this intervention in addressing homosexuality is limited, however, it has shown potential in managing male sexual dysfunctions. According to Badri (1984: 101), it is not viable to use this as a substantiating argument. Skinner contends that Muslims are unable to get advantages from the psychological knowledge originating from Western societies. The individual's decision to align with Badri stems from two primary

reasons. Firstly, he perceives Badri as a psychology framework deeply rooted in cultural influences. Secondly, he views Badri as the only comprehensive psychological approach that employs an experimental methodology devoid of any cultural prejudices. According to the individual in question, the origins of this phenomenon may be attributed to the teachings found in the Qur'an, which have been embraced by adherents of the Islamic faith. It is vital for individuals to possess a comprehensive comprehension of their own identity. Drawing upon the intellectual heritage of Islam may be advantageous in this regard. Skinner's suggested model delves into mental processes to a greater extent than conventional Western concepts. This enables it to be seen as a comprehensive phenomenon, in contrast to its cultural and social determinants. The user's text "BF" could be rewritten as "boyfriend" in an academic Skinner espouses principles originating from Western intellectual traditions, while also introducing his own conceptualization of mental well-being. Within this particular setting, there is a strong emphasis placed on the need of exercising caution, and there is also a notable encouragement for its use. According to Skinner, it seems that these principles have not yet achieved their maximum potential, indicating the need for more research and development. According to Agilkaya (2019, p. 30),

In the year 1981, the individual in question encountered muzaffer Özak, who held the esteemed position of sheikh inside the halveti-surgery. This encounter led to the individual's conversion to the Islamic faith, afterwards adopting the name Ragp Baba. Robert Frager is a distinguished authority in the field of social psychology, duly acknowledged for his expertise in this domain. The publication titled "The Transpersonal" emerged in the state of California during the 1970s. He was the first individual to create the Institute of Psychology. Over time, the institution underwent a transformation and evolved into a university. He is regarded as a trailblazer in the domain of interpersonal psychology, having played a major role in its establishment. Numerous scholarly investigations have been conducted on salient facets within the domain of positive psychology. Following his conversion to Sufism, he successfully secured employment as a surgeon-halveti sheikh inside the United States. The individual in question completed his educational pursuits at the Transpersonal Institute, an establishment that he himself established. Additionally, he also devised a Sufi therapy approach, as documented by Frager (2015:1). Enhancing the ego is a prevalent objective within modern psychotherapy, with the intention of bolstering the patient's sense of self. Frager says that under Sufi psychology, the objective is to eradicate the notion of ego. The branch of psychology that focuses on the person aims to enhance the organization, transformation, and development of that individual.

Belhi, widely regarded as the first figure in the field of psychiatry, spearheaded the development and implementation of diagnostic methodologies for mental disorders. In the subsequent phase, the individual will engage in a process of soul purification, facilitated by the practice of mysticism, with the aim of addressing both bodily and spiritual afflictions. This purification is vital to the individual's overall development, enabling them to transcend the state of self-realization. A range of methodologies, techniques, and methodologies were used in facilitating the guidance and mentorship of individuals inside dervish lodges and zawiyas. In recent times, there has been a significant amount of global study conducted on several topics like Islam, spirituality, mysticism, and the psychology of the soul. The exclusive focus on the brain and mind within the realm of psychology extends beyond the biological underpinnings of the discipline, as it neglects the consideration of the soul. It is important to note that current psychology lacks the capacity to provide an explanation for the concept of the soul, since there is little information available on this matter. The phenomenon has resulted in the development of a perspective that is deemed unacceptable. Currently, it would be advantageous for the field of psychology to adopt a framework that incorporates the concept of the spirit and redefines the science of the soul as pertaining to the spirit, rather than just focusing on scientific principles. This shift would allow psychology to direct its research and investigations towards the exploration of this particular domain. In this discourse, the integration of ancient wisdom, experiential knowledge, traditional practices, and empirical research will be expounded upon, using the methodologies and approaches of modern psychology. The matter at hand has significant significance, not alone for the Islamic world, which is now facing imminent decline, but also for the whole of mankind.

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